

THE MOST COMPREHENSIVE EUROPEAN DATASET OF AGRICULTURAL LONG-TERM EXPERIMENTS

AGRICULTURAL LONG-TERM EXPERIMENTS (LTES)

LTES are **crucial** for research. They monitor long-term effects of land management and pedo-climatic conditions on crop production and soil resources.

A MINE OF INFORMATION

About 50 categories, e.g. land use, research theme, management operations and soil parameters of LTES.

A BROAD VIEW

616 sites in 30 countries.
508 still ongoing
The oldest started **1843**
(Broadbalk experiment, UK)

AUTHORS

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Katja Klumpp (2022)

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Continuous Updating

The LTE metadataset is located in an interactive LTE overview map (<http://lte.bonares.de>), allowing users to find LTES based on specific combinations of practices relevant for networking and information exchange.

EJP SOIL INNOVATION HIGHLIGHTS

TOWARDS CLIMATE-SMART SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT OF AGRICULTURAL SOILS

EJP SOIL is a European Joint Programme on Agricultural Soil Management addressing key societal challenges including climate change and future food supply. <https://ejpsoil.eu/>

The goal is to improve the understanding of agricultural soil management by finding synergies in research, strengthening research communities and raising public awareness.

1100+ experts, 24 countries, addressing multiple aspects of soil management across different European agroecosystems.

EJP SOIL FRAMEWORK PROGRAMME

This project has received funding by EU H2020 European Joint programme EJP SOIL (grant agreement no. 869625). EJP SOIL WP7 synthesizes research outputs and a dedicated T7.3 has developed the most comprehensive database on LTEs in Europe and continue to update with new LTEs.

WORKPACKAGE COORDINATOR:

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TARGET EJP SOIL EXPECTED IMPACT AND EU MISSION SOIL OBJECTIVES

Supporting harmonised European soil information

Strengthening scientific capacities and cooperation

Mission SOIL: Conserve soil organic carbon stocks

HIGHLIGHT FACTS FROM:

EJP SOIL
framework programme

Applicability:
all climatic zones according to
Metzger et al. (2005)
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1466-822X.2005.00190.x>

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